

Direct ink writing of lightweight 3D structures from alkali-activated waste fiberglass and glass microsphere fillers

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the upcycling of glass waste into sustainable materials using additive manufacturing. The direct ink writing technique was used to 3D print structures from waste fiberglass activated with 3 M or 5 M NaOH. All inks showed shear-thinning behavior after 3 h of mixing, ensuring good printability. Printed structure with 5 M NaOH achieved higher compressive strength (5.2 MPa). Incorporation of glass microsphere fillers, synthesized from waste soda-lime glass via flame synthesis, improved print quality and reduced density. The printed structures displayed good layer adhesion and defect-free morphology. Thermal treatment at 800 °C produced porous glass ceramics with a foaming effect. Low molarity and microsphere incorporation minimized foaming while preserving the 3D structure. Final products had porosities of 88–93 %, bulk densities of 0.17–0.3 g/cm³, and compressive strengths of 1.6–3.2 MPa, demonstrating their potential as lightweight, sustainable building materials.

1. Introduction

Additive manufacturing (AM), commonly known as 3D printing, stands out from traditional casting techniques by eliminating the necessity for molds. This innovation simplifies the manufacturing process of complex geometric structures, enabling customized production on a large scale [1]. Among the various AM technologies, direct ink writing (DIW), also known as robocasting, is considered the most adaptable approach for materials development. DIW operates as an extrusion-based 3D printing process, utilizing a computer-controlled model to guide the printing head layer by layer. It employs a suspension of powders, called inks, extruded through a nozzle under external pressure. This technique selectively deposits material only in the areas needed to create the final shape of the desired object [2,3]. DIW is efficient due to its good resolution, cost-effectiveness, low material requirements, ease of operation, and versatility. It paves the way for printing a wide variety of materials, including ceramics, glass, metals, polymers, and composites [4–6].

The ink must exhibit appropriate rheological properties to facilitate easy extrusion through the nozzle and ensure the deposited ink

maintains its shape. Specifically, the ink should demonstrate shear-thinning behavior, where its viscosity decreases as the shear rate increases under external force during extrusion. Subsequently, upon deposition, as the shear rate decreases, the viscosity should increase to allow the filament to maintain and retain its intended shape [2,7]. The rheological characteristics of the ink can be modified by adjusting parameters such as solid loading, solvent concentration, particle size distribution, type and concentration of additives, etc. This enables the production of materials with intricate patterns, high spatial resolution, and customizable mechanical properties [7–9].

The incomplete glass recycling processes due to quality requirements have led to the emergence of open-loop recycling (upcycling), where the development of new valuable products from unrecyclable glass, distinct from the original, becomes fundamental in addressing recycling limitations [10,11]. The upcycling procedure involves alkali activation, wherein the glass is dissolved in an alkali solution that disrupts the Si-O-Al and Si-O-Si bonds, resulting in the formation of Al-OH and Si-OH groups, which later condense and contribute to the production of an alkaline aluminosilicate gel [12,13]. The gel might include calcium silicate hydrates (C-S-H), incorporating glass with low alumina and high

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calcium content, such as soda lime glass [14]. When glasses with high alumina content are used, a mixture of calcium and sodium aluminium silicate hydrates is produced [15]. Once hardened, this inorganic material is highly suitable for various applications in the construction industry, water treatment, and waste immobilization [10,16–20].

With appropriate preparation and modification, alkali activation of waste glass can yield inks exhibiting shear-thinning behavior (pseudoplasticity) suitable for direct ink writing (DIW), presenting a promising approach for upcycling waste materials. Previous studies have focused predominantly on the direct ink writing of laboratory-synthesized glass powder mixed with non-reactive organic binders such as gelatine [21], organic polymers, and resins [22,23]. Waste-based glass having bentonite as an additive was mixed with distilled water to produce inks that are printed and sintered into porous glass-ceramics [24]. These studies indicate that incorporating organic binders often leads to unstable printed samples with low strength, highlighting the necessity for a post-processing step, such as sintering.

Although limited literature exists, a few studies have shown that alkali activation of glass particles can produce scaffolds with adequate strength, eliminating the need for sintering. The extrudability and smoothness of printing can vary depending on the composition of the glass and the ink formulation. For example, Mokhtar et al. successfully printed alkali-activated magnetite-containing glass activated with 5 M NaOH, which resulted in easy extrusion and stable prints for water treatment applications [25]. In another case, waste borosilicate glass activated with 2.5 M NaOH requires incorporating additives like porous glass microspheres to enhance print stability, filament sagging, and compressive strength [26]. Additives can improve suspension homogeneity and flowability when the alkali attack lowers gelation on the glass surfaces. Spherical particles, like glass microspheres and polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA), have proven to enhance viscosity, optimize flowability during the extrusion process, and increase the porosity, creating a lightweight and more functional scaffold [27–29]. Rheology modifiers like polyethylene glycol (PEG) in the inks can facilitate easy extrusion at low pressure by decreasing the surface tension of water in the solution and binding particles to create higher viscosity without affecting the alkali-induced reaction [7,30,31]. The variety of waste glass composition, activation mechanisms, and printing parameters significantly impacts rheological properties and extrudability in direct ink writing; however, these factors remain underexplored and require further investigation.

This study explores how alkali concentration and the addition of glass microsphere fillers influence gelation and rheological properties in direct ink writing of alkali-activated waste fiberglass for producing lightweight scaffolds. Waste fiberglass contains sufficient CaO and Al₂O₃, resulting in the formation of mixed sodium or calcium-based aluminosilicate networks when activated with moderately lower concentrated alkali solution (3 M and 5 M), leading to the formation of a stable SiO₄ and AlO₄ tetrahedra, so-called ‘zeolite-like gels’, resembling product typically found in geopolymers [32–35]. The formation of mixed gels enhances the rate of gelation and hardening, resulting in improved mechanical strength and rapid structural development [20,36,37]. Consequently, 3D printing of these inks presents a sustainable approach to fabricating lightweight 3D structures with precisely designed porosities and load-bearing capabilities with minimal material [29]. This method has potential applications in the construction industry, as it can also reduce CO₂ emissions by providing an alternative building material to ordinary Portland cement. Moreover, using low-concentration alkalis offers a more sustainable alternative to many alkali-activated and geopolymer materials that rely on high alkali concentrations and alkali silicates [38–40].

Glass microspheres (GM) derived from waste soda-lime glass and produced using a flame synthesis technique were incorporated in the inks to improve printability and decrease density for lightweight applications. Their high temperature stability and corrosion resistance make them ideal for insulation and acoustic uses in construction

[41–43]. Furthermore, this study explores the thermal transformation of the printed samples when fired at 800 °C to expand their potential application areas

2. Methodology

2.1. Raw materials

Commercial-grade NaOH pellets (Honeywell, Fluka >98 % purity) were dissolved in distilled water to prepare 3 M and 5 M NaOH solutions. The waste fiberglass was obtained from Johns Manville, Slovakia, a.s. in Trnava. Soda-lime glass waste was collected from Vetropack Nemšová s.r.o, a container glass producer in Slovakia. The materials were initially crushed and then sieved through a 40 µm analytical sieve. The chemical composition of the waste glasses is provided in Table 1. The measurements were conducted with a Bruker S8 TIGER XRF spectrometer (Germany) after fusing the glass powders with lithium tetraborate. Data analysis was carried out using QUANT-Express software. Glass microspheres were prepared from discarded soda lime glass by flame synthesis techniques. The process operated under vacuum pressure (−1.5 hPa), with a spacer of 0.95 mm for the vacuum powder feeder. The powder feed rate was set at 2.5 g/min. Details of the production process have been described in the study of Mokhtar et.al [44].

2.2. Ink preparation

Fig. 1 presents the process for ink preparation. The initial ink formulation was achieved by mixing waste fiberglass powder with a 3 M or 5 M NaOH solution. Polyethylene glycol (PEG 1000, Sigma-Aldrich, Italy) with an average molecular weight of 1000 g/mol was added to the suspension to enhance the rheological properties, accounting for 4.5 % of the overall ink weight. The suspension was mixed for 3 h at 500 rpm. The incorporation of GMs in the 3 M NaOH-activated inks with up to 20 wt. % resulted in a dry, disintegrated ink. Therefore, GMs, comprising 25 % by weight of the fiberglass powder, were added only to the 5 M NaOH-activated samples after a 3-hour mixing period. This mix was thoroughly homogenized by mixing it for 5 min at 500 rpm before printing. The composition of the inks is summarised in Table 2.

After mixing for 3 h, the inks were transferred into a 30cc syringe and mounted on a direct ink-writing printer (Delta Wasp 2040 Turbo, Italy). A preprinted model in STL format was imported into a slicer software, where the printing paths were generated as a G-code file. The syringe was connected to a pneumatic extrusion system, with the extrusion pressure regulated by a dispenser. The inks were then extruded under ambient conditions onto a plastic substrate to ensure optimal adhesion, utilizing a conical nozzle with a tip diameter of 840 µm (Nordson Italia, Milano, Italy). The 3D structures designed for printing feature overlapping zig-zag filaments with 0, 90 orientations, maintaining an interspacing of 0.7 mm between adjacent layers along the z-axis and a 1.6 mm in-plane spacing between filaments along the x-y axis. Depending on the ink formulation, the nozzle was operated at a movement speed ranging from 3 to 5 mm/s, with an air pressure set between 0.3 and 0.6 bar.

The 3D structures were printed to dimensions of approximately 20 × 20 × 7.2 mm³ and placed in an oven at 40 °C for 48 h. Following this initial curing phase, the printed samples were allowed to cure for an additional 14 days at ambient temperature to further ensure complete reaction and hardening [45]. To analyze the impact of heat treatment, the 3D structures were fired in a muffle furnace at 800 °C, employing a heating rate of 5 °C/min, along with a one-hour isothermal dwell period. Samples were retrieved from the muffle furnace after cooling, the edges were cut, and the specimens were gently polished in preparation for characterisation.

Table 1
Chemical composition of the investigated glass wastes expressed in wt. %.

	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	CaO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	Fe ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	MgO	B ₂ O ₃	SO ₃
Waste Fiber	56.1	13.9	22.2	0.6	0.6	0.3	0.3	2.1	3.9	–
Glass (WFG)	±0.6	±0.2	±0.1	±0.1	±0.1	±0.03	±0.1	±0.1	±0.02	
Glass	69.9	1.9	11.1	13.5	0.8	0.4	0.1	2.0	–	0.3 ± 0.1
Microspheres (GMs)	±0.7	±0.3	±0.2	±0.2	±0.1	±0.02	±0.05	±0.1		

Fig. 1. Schematic presentation of ink preparation and DIW additive manufacturing process.

Table 2
Formulation details of the prepared inks.

Ink name	WFG (g)	GMs (g)	NaOH solution		PEG (g)
			Concentration (M)	Weight added (g)	
3M-FG	20	–	3	9	1.31
5M-FG	20	–	5		
5M-FG-GM	20	5			

2.3. Characterization

X-ray diffraction was performed on the fine powders of the raw materials, printed samples, and fired samples over a 2θ range of 10–70° using CuK α radiation of 40 kV and 40 mA (Bruker D8 Advance, Bruker AXS, Karlsruhe, Germany). The step size was 0.05°, and the step time was 1 s. The phase identification was performed using Match! Program package (Crystal Impact GbR, Bonn, Germany), supported by data from Powder Diffraction File (PDF)-2 database (International Centre for Diffraction Data, Newtown Square, PA, USA). Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR, spectrum 3, Perkin-Elmer, USA) was performed on the raw materials and powdered samples in the 400 cm⁻¹–4000 cm⁻¹ range, with a resolution of 2 cm⁻¹, to analyse their bond structure.

The rheological characteristics of inks were investigated at ambient temperature using a rheometer (HAAKE MARS III, Thermo-Fisher Scientific, USA), with a 35 mm flat plate geometry and a 1 mm gap. The measurements were conducted at intervals of 2 h, 2.5 h, 3 h, and 3.5 h after the start of mixing. The viscosity of the inks was evaluated as a function of shear rate, ranging from 0.1 to 100 s⁻¹. To assess the thixotropic properties of the inks at various time intervals, a three-stage measurement protocol was employed, each lasting 60 s: (Stage I) at a low shear rate of 0.01 s⁻¹, (Stage II) at a high shear rate 1 s⁻¹, and (Stage III) again at a low shear rate of 0.01 s⁻¹. Additionally, modulus recovery was performed on selected inks through 3 steps as a function of strain percentage: (step I at 0.1 %, step II at 1 %, and step III at 0.1 %). Furthermore, the storage and loss moduli were analysed by a strain amplitude sweep, varying strain from 0.001 % to 100 % at a frequency of

1 Hz.

Scanning electron microscopy (FEI Quanta 200 ESEM, Eindhoven, Netherlands) equipped with a Dual Backscattered Electron Detector (BSD) was used to examine morphological and microstructural features. The analysis was conducted at an accelerating voltage of 20 kV and a beam current of 0.29 nA. Mechanical strength tests were performed on printed and fired samples. Compressive strength tests were conducted using a universal testing machine (Quasar 25, Galdabini S.p.a., Cardano al Campo, Italy), operated at a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min. The load applied to the 3D structures was perpendicular to the printing direction. The fired samples were cut and polished gently before the compressive strength test. The geometric density of samples was calculated based on the weight-to-volume ratios of a regular 3D structure, following precise measurements of weights and dimensions with an analytical balance and a digital caliper. The apparent density of the 3D structures and the true density of the powdered samples were assessed using a helium pycnometer (Anton Paar, Ultrapyc 3000). The calculated density values were subsequently used to determine the samples' total, open, and closed porosity according to Eqs. (1), 2 & 3, respectively.

$$\text{total porosity (\%)} = \left(1 - \frac{\rho_{\text{geometric}}}{\rho_{\text{true}}}\right) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{open porosity (\%)} = \left(1 - \frac{\rho_{\text{geometric}}}{\rho_{\text{Apparent}}}\right) \times 100 \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Closed porosity (\%)} = \text{Total Porosity (\%)} - \text{Open Porosity (\%)} \quad (3)$$

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Alkali activation of waste fiberglass

The waste fiberglass powders consist of finely ground, irregular-shaped particles with a density of 2.7 ± 0.01 g/cm³ (Fig. 2a). The produced glass microsphere is a mixture of hollow and solid glass, having a density of 1.2 ± 0.001 g/cm³ with different particle size ranges (Fig. 2a & b).

The alkali activation of waste fiberglass using a 3 M NaOH solution leads to the formation of vaugnatite (CaAl(OH)SiO₄ PDF #71–1795) and

Fig. 2. SEM images of a) waste fiberglass powders, b) GMs, and c) particle size distribution histograms of GMs.

thermonatrite ($\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ PDF#76–910), as depicted in Fig. 3. Increasing the alkali concentration generates additional peaks corresponding to thermonatrite and promotes the formation of sodium aluminosilicate hydrate $\text{Na}_3\text{Al}_3\text{Si}_3\text{O}_{12} (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ PDF#84–0590).

The FTIR spectra shown in Fig. 3b further illustrate the formation of a mixed interconnected zeolite-like gel that primarily consists of N-A-S-H and C-A-S-H, typical products of geopolymer-like and alkali-activated materials [10]. The sharpening of the bands in the range between $800\text{--}1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ after activation suggests structural ordering within the glass. The bands observed between $900\text{--}1100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are related to the asymmetric tension of the Si-O-Si and Si-O-Al groups. These peaks are characteristic of C-A-S-H and N-A-S-H mixed structures [46]. The slight shift of the peaks to lower wavelength ($960\text{ to }950\text{ cm}^{-1}$) when the alkali molarity increases shows a more significant dissolution of the glass structure. Additionally, hydration bands corresponding to O-H stretching and bending are observable at 1650 cm^{-1} and in the range of $2500\text{--}3700\text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. The band around 1450 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of carbonate compounds [18].

3.2. Rheological properties

The rheological behavior of the inks was evaluated at different time intervals to compare the differences between the 3 M and 5 M activated

inks. It was found that the viscosity of all inks increased over time, suggesting the dissolution of glass resulted in a time-dependent thickening of the gel (Fig. 4a). The decrease in viscosity with increasing shear rate indicates shear-thinning behavior, where the noise or spikes observed at higher shear rates are likely due to structural breakdown within the paste, causing temporary resistance to flow as the internal structure collapses under shear [47,48]. The viscosity of the 5M-FG was higher than that of 3M-FG with increased shear rate, demonstrating enhanced pseudoplastic characteristics. Following the addition of glass microsphere fillers, the viscosity of 5M-FG-GM ink decreased, as the fillers acted as a lubricant, minimizing the internal friction within the gel matrix. Nevertheless, the shear-thinning behaviour continued to be observed as the shear rate increased.

The viscosity recovery analysis further validated the pseudoplastic nature of these inks (Fig. 4b). At a constant low shear rate, the viscosity at 3 and 3.5 h showed an initial increase within the first 10 s, reflecting the structural rebuilding as the more rigid ink transitions to a steady-state viscosity. As the shear rate increased (step II), the viscosity decreased significantly. The inks regained a greater portion of their initial viscosity after shear release (step III), particularly evident after the 2.5 h period. Viscosity recovery occurred very rapidly within the first 10 s after shear release, followed by fluctuations before eventually stabilizing when considering 3 h and 3.5 h intervals. The 5M-FG ink

Fig. 3. X-ray diffraction patterns (a) and FTIR spectra (b) of waste fiberglass and after alkali activation with or without GM at different concentrations of NaOH.

Fig. 4. a) Viscosity as a function of shear rate for different aging times, illustrating how viscosity changes over time. Viscosity increases with aging time, shown by the color gradient from light to dark (light red to dark red for 3M-FG; light blue to dark blue for 5M-FG) and black and grey for 5M-FG-GM. b) Viscosity recovery analysis of the inks at various time points.

reached stability within 20 s at 3 h and within 15 s at the 3.5 h mark. In contrast, the 3M-FG ink displayed more pronounced fluctuations in both time frames. In thixotropic suspensions, shear induces complex structural changes, and the structural recovery at rest differs from the gradual

reduction of shear, leading to distinct structural buildup pathways [49]. Thus, the viscosity fluctuations observed a few seconds after shear reduction can be attributed to the highly thixotropic and viscoelastic nature of the inks, combined with the complex structural rearrangement

Fig. 5. Storage modulus (G') and loss modulus (G'') analysis of different open times of the inks, a) 3M-FG, b) 5M-FG, c) 5M-FG-GM, and d) modulus recovery of 3M-FG and 5M-FG at 3hr.

dynamics of the aluminosilicate gel network and rheology modifier. The incorporation of glass microsphere fillers showed similar thixotropic characteristics but reduced fluctuation in the viscosity curve of 5M-FG. The stability can be attributed to the filler's lubricant effect to alter the rearrangement of the gel network and provide mechanical support during recovery, thus improving the highly thixotropic ink into an elastic solid system [50–52].

To enhance the understanding of extrudability and shape recovery, the storage modulus (G') and loss modulus (G'') were assessed as a function of strain along with their recovery at various stages. Identifying the flow point (yield stress) where the G' and G'' intersect provides insight into the solid-fluid transition, which is critical for ease of extrusion during printing [47]. Figs. 5a, 5b & 5c depict the strain vs modulus curve of the inks. The crossover values of G' and G'' increased over time. 3M-FG (Fig. 5a) showed multiple crossing points at 3 h and 3.5 h. The crossover points at higher modulus happened at lower strain, suggesting initial rearrangement of a certain network or loose clusters, while the dominant network breakdown and flow point occurred in the strain range of 0.2–0.3%. The multiple crossover points can be attributed to its time-dependent viscosity and intricate reorganisation of internal structures within the ink under varying shear rates or stresses [49, 53–55]. Conversely, the crossover points are higher in value for 5M-FG (Fig. 5b), indicating that higher stress is required to initiate the solid-liquid transition. The drop observed in the plots of 3.5 h for both 3M-FG and 5M-FG (Fig. 5a and b) is related to the sudden microstructural breakdown and rapid changes in viscoelasticity or wall slip due to less adhesion, as the ink becomes more rigid through time. Incorporating glass microsphere fillers improves flowability by reducing the crossover point of 5G-GM at 3 hrs from 151 Pa to 86.7 Pa, suggesting their potential to improve flowability and ease of extrusion (Fig. 5c).

According to the 3 h modulus recovery analysis (Fig. 5d), the storage modulus (G') exceeded the loss modulus (G'') at lower strain levels (step I). After strain was applied (step II) slightly higher than the flow points,

the ink transitioned to a more liquid-like state, characterised by $G'' > G'$. In step III, more than 50% of G'' recovered within the first 15 s, while still in the liquid state ($G'' > G'$). However, after 15 s, G' sharply increased to a higher magnitude, showing faster solidification and higher structural strength. In the case of 3 M-FG, once the stress is removed, G' remained greater than G'' and more than 50% of the modulus G' recovered by the end of 60 s, indicating slower gel network reorganisation than 5 M-FG.

Rheological analysis revealed that the inks became suitable for printing after 3 h of mixing. Visual observation confirmed that the inks remained extrudable up to 3 h and 50 min. The incorporation of glass microspheres reduced the viscosity of 5FG-GM; however, after 3 h and 30 min, the viscosity increased due to the reaction of GMs with the alkali solution. This increase in viscosity presented challenges for rheological measurements, as it prevented the application of high shear and resulted in inadequate adhesion between the rheometer plates.

3.3. Direct ink writing of the 3D structures

The optical microscope images of the printed samples (Fig. 6) showed no defects or cracks in the structures. The top view displays that the 3M-FG sample (Fig. 6a) has well-defined spacing between the filaments, showcasing uniformity and continuity with a thickness of filaments in a range not far from the nozzle diameter. The sectioned side view of this sample (Fig. 6b) demonstrates that the filaments are formed without sagging, indicating a rapid solidification process following extrusion. This suggests that the inks possess adequate stiffness to support the weight of the upper layer while maintaining their shape. Similar characteristics are observed in the 5M-FG sample (Fig. 6c and 6d).

However, Fig. 6c illustrates that the filament thickness in the 5M-FG is slightly higher than the nozzle diameter, and a narrow filament gap. According to step III of the loss and storage modulus recovery (Fig. 5d), the ink initially behaves like a liquid for a few seconds after extrusion,

Fig. 6. Optical microscopy images of the top and section view of (a & b) 3M-FG, (c & d) 5M-FG and (e & f) 5M-FG-GM.

causing die swelling and narrowing the space between filaments, before rapidly hardening. Image analysis in Fig. 6 shows that the highest filament thickness-to-nozzle diameter ratio in the 3D structures is approximately 1.42, which falls within the accepted range for good print quality (1.0 to 1.5) [47,56–58]. Moreover, printing parameters influence the process. For example, due to its increased viscosity, extrusion pressure for the 5M-FG ink was higher (around 0.6 bar) and printing speed was slightly reduced (3mm/s) compared to the 3M-FG (approximately 0.3 bar). These conditions, coupled with side effects such as bubble formation caused by ongoing gelation, resulted in variation in filament thickness in all the inks. The incorporation of glass microsphere fillers in the 5M-FG inks reduced the extrusion pressure to 0.4 bar, indicating an improvement in the ink's flow properties. This can be attributed to the spherical morphology and low density of the glass microspheres, which contribute to a reduction in internal friction and enhance the shear-thinning behaviour of the ink. Moreover, glass microspheres aid in maintaining the structural integrity of the printed features, enabling better control over filament thickness and inter-filament spacing, as evident in the well-defined geometries shown in Fig. 6e and 6f.

The SEM top-view images of 3M-FG (Fig. 7a, b) and 5M-FG (Fig. 7e, f) reveal the presence of unreacted fiberglass particles embedded in the alkali-activated gel matrix. In the case of 5M-FG, the filaments exhibited pores, and the gel appeared significantly darker due to a more concentrated gel formation compared to that observed in 3M-FG. The sectioned side views for both 3M-FG and 5M-FG (Fig. 7c, d, g & h) highlight the presence of small pores resulting from air trapped during the syringe filling process or from PEG dissipation. In the case of 5M-FG-GM, the glass microspheres were well distributed and enclosed by the gel matrix activation process (Fig. 7e & f). The introduction of the glass microsphere occurred at the final stage of mixing, resulting in a minimal outer surface attack by the alkali, keeping the spherical shape as it is (Fig. 7k & l). Pores observed in the filaments are attributed to trapped air during printing and the detachment of GMs that were weakly bonded to the gel matrix and likely dislodged during cutting.

5M-FG formulation, which has a higher gel formation content

compared to 3M-FG, resulted in a total porosity of 55 % and a higher geometric density of 1.12 g/cm^3 , as shown in Table 3. Incorporating GMs decreased the geometric density to 0.98 g/cm^3 and the true density of 5FG-GM from 2.52 g/cm^3 to 2.42 g/cm^3 . This decrease in density is attributed to the increased volume occupied by the glass microspheres in the ink, contributing to higher total porosity. The open porosity, influenced by both the structural design and filament pores, increased as the alkali concentration increased.

The compressive strength of 5 M-FG is significantly higher than that of 3M-FG due to strong dissolution, resulting in a gel that binds unreacted glass particles tightly and creates a less porous filament. The reduction in compressive strength, following the addition of glass microsphere (5M-FG-GM), is linked to their inefficiency in transmitting the stress to the surrounding gel when a load is applied. This inefficiency results from the weak interface between the gel and glass microspheres (Fig. 7l), serving as a vulnerable point in the matrix. Consequently, this fragile interface can lead to gel failure, resulting in decreased compressive strength, as demonstrated in the studies [59,60].

The difference in ink preparation method, rheological properties, printing design, and parameters significantly affects the mechanical properties of the 3D printed structure. For example, low molarity activation of borosilicate glass resulted in scaffolds having a density of 0.77 g/cm^3 , a total porosity of $72 \pm 1 \%$, and a compressive strength of $1.5 \pm 0.2 \text{ MPa}$, while DIW of waste derived alkali activated glass resulted in a

Table 3
Density, porosity, and compressive strength of prepared 3D structures.

	3M-FG	5M-FG	5M-FG-GM
Geometric density (g/cm^3)	0.96 ± 0.04	1.12 ± 0.01	0.98 ± 0.03
Apparent density (g/cm^3)	2.59 ± 0.01	2.41 ± 0.01	2.24 ± 0.01
True density (g/cm^3)	2.64 ± 0.02	2.52 ± 0.01	2.42 ± 0.01
Total porosity (%)	64	55	60
Open porosity (%)	63	53	56
Closed porosity (%)	1	2	3
Compressive strength (MPa)	1.4 ± 0.1	5.2 ± 0.1	1.6 ± 0.1

Fig. 7. SEM images of printed structures a-d)3M-FG, e-h)5M-FG, i-l)5M-FG-GM.

geometric density of 0.8 g/cm^3 and true density of 2.86 g/cm^3 with 70 % porosity [25,26]. Geopolymer scaffolds prepared from metakaolin showed a porosity of 59.4 %, and compressive strength reached 4.71 MPa [7]. Incorporating a foaming agent in a geopolymer resulted in a geometric density of 0.75 g/cm^3 with a porosity of 65.6 % and a compressive strength of 3.2 MPa [30]. A direct foaming process commonly prepares lightweight alkali-activated materials by incorporating a foaming agent during the gelation period to create gases that evaporate when the gel hardens, leaving a porous space [18,61]. These lightweight materials possess porosity higher than 50 % with densities ranging from 0.2 to 1.4 g/cm^3 and compressive strength from 1 to 10 MPa, depending on the type of precursors and foaming methods used [61–65]. Consequently, it is possible to classify the printed structures discussed in this work under lightweight alkali-activated materials.

Furthermore, considering their mechanical properties, the printed samples demonstrate a well-balanced compressive strength-to-density trade-off with commercially available technical ceramic materials. All printed samples matched with lightweight insulating concrete, as depicted in Fig. 12. The compressive strength-to-density ratio can be further enhanced by optimizing the design of 3D structures to improve load-bearing capacity while increasing porosity, particularly for 5M-FG, which demonstrates a promising compressive strength compared to aerated concrete.

3.4. Effect of heat treatment

The heat treatment process effectively transforms the struts of the 3D structures into highly porous glass-ceramics, as demonstrated in Fig. 8. This transformation occurs when the hydrated products and carbonates in the aluminosilicate gel decompose, releasing water and gases. At the same time, unreacted glass particles undergo viscous flow upon reaching

above the glass transition temperature of fiberglass ($T_g \sim 680 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). Heat treatment above the T_g ($800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) with the softening and binding process, accompanied by some crystallization, forms a robust porous glass-ceramic matrix [10,66].

The top view of the 3M-FG-800 in Fig. 8a illustrates that a porous filament with limited expansion, preserving structural integrity and spacing between the filaments, was produced compared to the 5M-FG samples shown in Fig. 8b. Furthermore, the sectioned view in Fig. 8b shows that while the spacing is maintained, the filaments exhibit a highly porous nature. The 5M-FG samples, as depicted in Fig. 8b & c, demonstrated significant dimensional expansion, enabling the filaments to expand freely and closing the gap between the filaments, ultimately forming a cohesive porous monolithic foam. The difference in foaming intensity between the 3M-FG-800 and 5M-FG-800 samples can be attributed to the hydrated product after alkali activation, which creates more gases during the thermal decomposition of aluminosilicate hydroxyls and hydrated carbonates [66].

The expansion and formation of pores were also facilitated by incorporating PEG acting as a foaming inducer, promoting uniform foaming throughout the filaments. This uniform foaming effect is evident when comparing 5M-FG samples prepared by simple casting in a cube mold. As shown in Fig. 9b, the sample prepared without PEG exhibited non-uniform partial foaming on the top surface and densification at the bottom, leading to an irregular distribution of pores. In contrast, the sample with PEG (Fig. 9a) demonstrated uniform pore distribution. The open porosity, influenced by both the structural design and filament pores, increased as the alkali concentration increased.

The incorporation of glass microspheres resulted in notable bending and filament deformation, followed by spalling and surface cracking, as illustrated in Fig. 8e. The sectioned view in Fig. 8f reveals a porous structure with a slightly reduced expansion, indicated by the residual

Fig. 8. Optical microscope images of samples fired at $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; (a,b) 3M-FG-800. (c,d) 5M-FG-800; (e,f) 5M-FG-HGM-800.

Fig. 9. Optical microscope images of casted samples 5M-FG after firing at 800 °C, a) with PEG and b) without PEG addition.

open pores originating from the spacing between adjacent filaments compared to 5M-FG-800.

Table 4 highlights that 3M-FG-800 exhibits slightly higher compressive strength and geometric density compared to 5M-FG-800, mainly due to the presence of substantial closed porosity in the foamed filaments. 5M-FG-GM-800 displays open porosity and attains the highest density and compressive strength. 5M-FG containing PEG that was cast in a mold and fired at 800 °C (5M-FG-casted-800) has a geometric density that is 1.5 times higher than the printed and fired samples, with reduced total porosity exhibiting predominantly closed pores. In this context, the advantage of 3D printing lies in achieving a hierarchically porous 3D structure with uniformly distributed pores by reducing stress within the bubbles through the filament spaces, influencing the formation of open pores, ultimately resulting in a much lower density. However, further investigations are required to ensure that the samples retain their original shape with uniform expansion, avoiding deformation or loss of structural integrity during heat treatment.

The difference in pore sizes is evident in the SEM images of the fired samples, as depicted in Fig. 10. The top surface images of the filaments for both 3M-FG (Fig. 10a) and 5M-FG (Fig. 10b) reveal crystals embedded in the glass matrix. The sectioned images for 3M-FG (Fig. 10d) and 5M-FG (Fig. 10e) showcase the variability in porosity, with both open and closed pores present. Notably, pore sizes differ significantly, with pore sizes less than 100 μm predominantly found in 3M-FG, while large pores, from 120 μm–500 μm, are primarily associated with 5M-FG, significantly affecting the mechanical properties.

The top view of the SEM images in Fig. 10c & f show glass microspheres fully and partially embedded with glass matrix, concurrently retarding the propagation of cracks. The increases in density and compressive strength compared to 5M-FG-800 can be attributed to the softening during viscous flow sintering and crystallization of glass microspheres. It is worth noting that the inclusion of glass microspheres constrains foaming, an effect resulting from the crystallization process. As indicated in the work of Ding et al. [67]. Sinter crystallization promotes the densification and shrinkage of glass microspheres, relieving stress and leading to filament deformations such as slight bending and spalling (Fig. 8e). Additionally, the shrinkage of these glass

microspheres has caused the partial collapse of their spherical walls, as shown in Fig. 10c, which effectively enhances the open porosity with reduced pore sizes compared to 5M-FG-800, as illustrated in Fig. 10f.

The XRD diffraction patterns presented in Fig. 11 show all fired 3D structures contain wollastonite (CaSiO_3 , PDF#043–1460) Fig. 11 as the primary crystal phase. Notably, the intensity of the wollastonite peaks increases significantly in samples containing glass microspheres. These samples exhibit peaks associated with Nepheline ($\text{NaSi}_3\text{AlO}_8$, PDF#10–0393), resulting from the crystallization of glass microspheres, which influenced the mechanical properties compared to 5M-FG-800.

The density of all fired samples is below 0.3 g/cm^3 and the total porosity of all samples exceeds 88 %, consisting mainly of open and closed pores. Fig. 12 illustrates that the densities of all fired samples are comparable to those of glass foams they significantly demonstrate higher compressive strength. Their combination of lightweight character and the presence of hierarchical porosity makes glass-ceramics well-suited for thermal and acoustic insulation applications, especially in designs featuring specially engineered geometries [68,69]. Table 5 presents the mechanical properties of porous glass-ceramics produced using various processing methods, along with a comparison to the porous ceramic fabricated through 3D printing of alkali-activated waste fiberglass.

4. Conclusion

Waste fiberglass inks, created through an alkaline activation process, have been effectively used to print a 3D structure exhibiting no defects. Rheological analysis indicated that all the inks showed shear-thinning behaviour with high viscosity and modulus retention after extrusion, enabling them to maintain their shape. These 3D structures exhibit a higher compressive strength-to-density ratio, particularly for the 5 M-FG (1.12 g/cm^3 and 5.2 MPa) compared to 3M-FG, making them well-suited for various applications in lightweight construction materials. The integration of glass microspheres has not only enhanced rheological properties and printability but also resulted in a 12.5 % reduction in bulk density. While this reduction led to a decrease in strength, it presents valuable opportunities for further ink optimization. To expand

Table 4

Density, porosity, and compressive strength of prepared samples by DIW printing and casting process, followed by firing at 800 °C.

	Geometric density (g/cm^3)	Apparent density (g/cm^3)	True density (g/cm^3)	Total porosity (%)	Open porosity (%)	Closed porosity (%)	Compressive strength (MPa)
3M-FG-800	0.21 ±0.08	0.36 ±0.09	2.58 ±0.04	91.7	41.7	50.0	2.6 ±0.2
5M-FG-800	0.17 ±0.01	0.40 ±0.11	2.32 ±0.03	92.8	58.6	34.1	1.6 ±0.1
5M-FG-GM-800	0.27 ±0.02	1.40 ±0.1	2.40 ±0.01	88.7	80.7	8.0	3.2 ±0.1
5M-FG-PEG-casted-800	0.26 ±0.01	0.31 ±0.01	2.31 ±0.03	88.6	16.1	72.6	6.3 ±1

Fig. 10. The top and sectioned side SEM images of printed samples after firing at 800 °C and pore size counts of filaments; a,d) 3M-FG-800; b,e) 5M-FG-800 and c,f) 5M-FG-GM-800.

their potential applications, these printed samples were subjected to heat treatment at 800 °C, resulting in a porous glass ceramic with a porosity range of 88 % to 92 %, while maintaining structural integrity, specifically for 3M-FG-800. They possess low density (0.2 - 0.3 g/cm³) combined with high compressive strength (1.6 - 3.2 MPa). These glass-ceramics are characterised by their lightweight nature and high porosity. Optimization of the 3D structure and mix composition can improve their dimensional stability during heat treatment, positioning

them as ideal candidates for thermal and acoustic insulation or as filter media for water treatment, highlighting their versatility and practical applications.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Abel W. Ourgessa: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation,

Fig. 11. XRD patterns of printed samples after firing at 800 °C.

Fig. 12. Compressive strength/bulk density trade-off of printed and fired 3D structures computed using CES software package. (The values in brackets next to the labels represent the average density of the corresponding material in g/cm³).

Conceptualization. **Ahmed Gamal Abd-ElSatar:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Mokhtar Mahmoud:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Hamada Elsayed:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jozef Kraxner:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Funding

acquisition, Conceptualization. **Dusan Galusek:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Enrico Bernardo:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Table 5

Comparison of lightweight porous-glass ceramics properties between this study and literature reports.

Raw material	Method	Temperature (°C)	Density (g/cm ³)	Total Porosity (%)	Compressive strength (MPa)	Ref.
Waste container glass	Direct foaming using water glass as a foaming agent followed by sintering	800–850	0.34–0.46	81.6–88.9	0.9–2.7	[69]
Vitrified bottom ash/ soda-lime glass/borosilicate glass	Foaming by weak alkali activation followed by sintering	850–1000	0.53–0.73	71.9–80	1.5–3.7	[19]
Volcanic ash and discarded glass	Alkali activation followed by firing	950	0.37–0.75	72.1–86.2	2.0–4.6	[70]
Fluorescent lamp	Foaming by Alkali activation (2.5 M NaOH) followed by sintering	700	0.53–0.85	74–81.5	1–5.8	[71]
Waste fiberglass	Foaming by low alkali activation + foaming agent followed by sintering	700–800	0.51–0.86	66.1–79.0	1.5–2.2	[10]
Bottle glass cullet and coal ash	Powder sintering with 2 wt % SiC foaming agent	1000–1050	0.2–0.4	70–90	1.2–1.7	[72]
Soda-lime glass with NaOH pellets	Pressing and sintered	800	0.31	86	–	[73]
Waste fiberglass	alkali activation by 3 M /5 M NaOH (with or without GMs) + PEG and DIW followed by heat treatment.	800	0.17–0.27	88–92.8	1.6–3.1	This work

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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